

A Report of Fr. General's Visit to Pune

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1. Fr. General arrived by road from Mumbai with Frs. Vernon D’Cunha, Lisbert D’Souza and Pierre Belanger at 7.30pm. They were welcomed at the Grotto by DNC community, 95-year-old Ted Bowling being one of them, to the accompaniment of Chotanagpur tribal dance and with a Marathi shawl and Peshwa head gear. Before proceeding to the house he planted a tree at the premises of the Marian Grotto. All the materials used for the welcome and decorations were eco-friendly.

2. On 6th at 7am Fr. General blessed the “Centre for Ignatian Spirituality and Research” at De Nobili College. Fr. Rector gave a short speech about the Centre, the background for this initiative and about its objective. Fr. General also pointed out that the service of the Spiritual Exercises and the science of Discernment is the 1st of the Universal Apostolic Preferences. He underlined that without this basic foundation the works the Jesuits do cannot be called Jesuit work. Pope Francis too has stressed that these are also the preferences of the Church for its renewal and revitalization in our fast changing, technology-driven world. It is hoped

that the Centre will be able to provide short and long term courses once it is equipped with adequate facilities and staff.

3. Following the blessing Fr. General posed for a community photo of the world's largest formation community of the Jesuits. Diversity is the hallmark of DNC Community. This is not merely a diversity of languages and cultures, these young Jesuits represent the diversity of missions their provinces undertake. Despite these diversities they are united in mind and hearts and are friends in the Lord because of the spirit of the Spiritual Exercises that binds them together.

4.As Fr. General was proceeding for his breakfast, he stopped at the "Pope Francis Herbal Garden" that came into existence when Pope Francis promulgated "Laudato Si," inviting all to care for our Common Home. Incidentally 'Caring for our Common Home' is also one of the 4 UAP. In his interaction with the scholastics in the evening he referred to this point by saying that at the individual, community and institutional level there must be visible life style changes, conserving water, energy, avoiding the use of plastics and recycling the waste materials. He pointed out that each one needs to go through an ecological conversion not merely carry out certain projects.

5.The next program at DNC was at 4pm to 5.30pm. Fr. General addressed the Jesuit scholastics on the following and later interacted with them. The following were the main points which he elaborated in his talk:

6. Unity of life and mission: He said that some Jesuits considered mission as work. They were very busy doing things; they gave minimum time for community and prayer. He cited the example of our founding fathers at Venice while they were waiting to go to Jerusalem. Their work preceded

prayer, Eucharist and spiritual conversation. Some people ask why one should be a Jesuit if the same work can be done by the lay persons. The answer lies in the unity of life and mission which is crucial for the Jesuit. When they could not go to the Holy Land, they offered themselves to the Pope. They were spiritually free to accept as God's will whatever ministry the Holy Father asked them to carry out. The unity of life and mission and discernment are gifts given to the Society by the Holy Spirit. This helps us to live as friends in the Lord, superiors, directors of works, principals, deans and other members of the community. It is our responsibility to safeguard this gift in the Society. It is in this context, the recent General Congregations of the Society of Jesus have stressed the community itself as mission because it is in the community we experience this triple unity.

7. Some consequences for formation:

- We must live in a consistent way; we must walk the talk. We see so many scandals in the Church today. There is a mismatch between what we are and what we preach.
- We must be transparent. Everyone has sinned (Jn. Ch. 8: one who has not sinned...) Mistakes are liable to happen, but one must be open to his superiors. (importance of Examen, the manifestation of conscience)
- Community as mission draws from the unity of life and mission. Be an active and positive member of the community. Some give minimum time for the community. Jesuit community is a dynamic group. We change regularly according to the needs of the mission. Our life of unity will be manifest in the way we celebrate the Eucharist. The disciples of Emmaus. Formation must help us to grow in this unity of life and mission.

8. Discernment in common: No attachment to any place or anyone (offering to the Pope for the mission). Jesuits these days tend to get attached to work, province, place etc.

9. Another area of discernment is intellectual depth: Study in the Society is not for getting a degree but it is an instrument for better discernment. Hence intellectual formation is apostolic.

10. Obedience: In the Society, we do not ask, 'what do you like?' Obedience is an order. We search and find God's will and follow it. The superior who gives the orders pays attention to 'cura personalis and cura apostolica', the person and the circumstances. The superior is responsible for the life and mission of the person. Creativity is necessary and it is a gift from the Holy Spirit. Persons, places and circumstances have to be taken into consideration. Mission is not individualistic; there must be discernment between creativity and obedience.

11. What does the Society expect from the scholastics? Formation is also simultaneously probation. No one must be allowed to pronounce the profession unless he proves himself worthy. Constitutions Part 5, Ch. 2: [516] - 1. "No one will be admitted to any degree of belonging unless he is judged fit in the Lord. For profession it means thorough screening through protracted and exacting tests, and clearance from the General, who will have reports from other superiors and individuals whom he has asked to testify."

12. Our primary vocation is to consecrated life; priesthood is a means. In the Society coadjutor brothers and priests are primarily consecrated persons. They are incorporated into a community of consecrated persons and can be sent on a 95-year-old mission. The most important moment for a Jesuit is the Final Vows and not ordination or diaconate. In

the Formula of the vows, the requirement to be a member of the Society is that you “understand all things according to the Constitution.” (Pope Francis had asked the delegates of GC36 to look into the way we celebrate ordination, diaconate, final profession etc.)

13. Universal Apostolic Preferences must impact the life of each Jesuit. We must live the UAP, rooted in Christ. The only way is to follow Christ.

14. Why the Spiritual Exercises do not transform us? If you are a man of prayer, every ministry you are sent to will transform us. (Early in the morning Jesus went to a lonely place to pray. When his disciples looked for him they found him in prayer.). In his days, people of faith used religion to persecute him. It will not be different for his disciples. Jesus worked for the liberation of humanity. He has not given us an easy task. For following the footsteps of Jesus, the Society will pay a very high cost.

15. Youth (Universal Apostolic Preferences or UAP): The young people have a crucial role in the Church. The Church must listen to the youth and make space for them to contribute to the Church’s mission.

16. The UAP will have to be the “Locus Theologicus” of our life and mission, an experience of following Jesus the incarnated Son of God. We are entering into an era of change in the Society and the Church. The Pope has endorsed the UAP as also Church’s preferences. Now we must take responsibility for these preferences, whether it is development, ecology, migration or the youth. We need to make changes in our personal and institutional life; e.g. use of plastic, water, energy, consumerism etc.

17. Why doesn't The Spiritual Exercises transform us? Because we do not do the Examen as Ignatius would like us to do. We must do examen after every important moment of our day. After we preach to the people, we must examine ourselves; what about me? After teaching a class to the student, I must examine myself. There must be community and Institutional examens.

18. UAP must impact community, institution, formation and our own person. We must practice spiritual conversation in our weekly gathering and other deliberations. We must do it. Let us do it.

(Notes taken down by Edward Mudavassery SJ of Fr. General's talk to the DNC Scholastics on 6th March at 4.00 pm to 5.30pm)

(Contd from p. 25) (Because we needed a room to accommodate Fr. Vernon close to Fr. General's room). Even today, he continues to say that I live in the room next to the room where the General stayed.

Fr. General was very casually dressed and very simple in his approach and dealings. He enjoyed every meal and occasion organized in honour of him. It was a surprise to many of us to see that such a great personality in such a simple style moving around. It was very clear that he did not want/like any luxury, pomp and show.

Though on the one hand he enjoyed the hospitality and company of people around him, he was aware of his mission; he was up to his business and serious with regard to his visit. Without mincing words, he said all that he wanted to say about the Society and the vision of the Society. He is of the opinion that these goals can be achieved by working together as one society. We started discussing about the wonderful things he had told us. We were inspired by the ideals of his simple living and high thinking. We should practice the values he talked about so that we become true Jesuits. Working together as one community we have learned that such occasions are moments of grace and our spirit was uplifted. We await the next visit of our General. **-Fr Jacob Kulangara SJ**